

Targeting and activation of monocytes by liposomes with TLR7 agonists

Daniel Zucker^{1,*}, Simon Skjøde Jensen², Houman Pourhassan², Jeanette E. Wern², Roberto Maj³, Alcide Barberis³, and Thomas Lars Andresen¹

¹Department of Micro- and Nanotechnology, Center for Nanomedicine and Theranostics, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby 2800, Denmark.

²Immune cell Targeting, Bioneer, Hoersholm 2970, Denmark.

³Telormedix SA, Bioggio 6934, Switzerland.

*To whom the correspondence should be addressed., e-mail: zucker@posteo.de

Short title: Liposome targeting of monocytes

Keywords

Liposome, immunotherapy, surface charge, drug delivery, monocyte, TLR7, cytokine

Abstract

Targeting drugs to specific cells of the immune system is a promising approach for improving the effect of immune modulating drugs. Monocytes play an essential role in a number of diseases due to their immune regulating properties and the ability of monocytes to differentiate into dendritic cells and macrophages, which makes them highly important for immunotherapy, e.g. in treatment of cancer and inflammatory conditions. The purpose of the present study was to develop immune modulating liposomes that specifically target and activate monocytes in the blood. We have discovered a new monocyte targeting mechanism by screening a high number of liposomal formulations, which after physicochemical characterization were analyzed in fresh whole human blood for association with immune cell subsets. In addition, TLR7 agonists were incorporated into the liposomal membrane by hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions. Monocyte activation by liposomes formulated with TLR7 agonists was tested by measuring cytokine secretion. Liposomes with zeta potentials within a range of 30-40 mV and diameters of 100-200 nm showed a highly preferential association with monocytes compared to lymphocytes and granulocytes. Moreover, liposomes with TLR7 agonists potently activated and specifically targeted monocytes in human blood. Therefore, these novel immune stimulating liposomes are promising candidates for cancer immunotherapy.

Introduction

A majority of vaccines used today are based on technologies that utilize classical adjuvants such as alum that were introduced almost a century ago. There is a strong need for novel vaccine technologies that utilizes the new insight in biomaterials and immunology that has emerged during the last decade.¹

A major advance for the understanding of the mechanisms of innate immunity is the identification of Toll Like Receptors (TLRs), which recognize pathogens that attempt to infect the host. TLR activation is essential for boosting an adaptive immune response that allows the immune system to fight the infection and eliminate the pathogen. Natural and synthetic TLR agonists have proven to be highly interesting for future vaccine technologies, and many TLR agonists are in clinical trial today, or already being used for treatment of patients. TLR7 is expressed in human plasmacytoid and myeloid dendritic cells, B-cells and monocytes and is localized in the endosome membrane, where it is activated during viral infections.² TLR7 responses are often impaired in both infectious diseases and cancer and TLR7 activation has been suggested as an important target for future vaccine and cancer immunotherapy.³

While there are established TLR7 agonists on the market, e.g. imiquimod which is used for topical treatment of skin cancer, and several more are in clinical development, many new TLR7 agonists are continuously being reported. TMXs is a new class of TLR7 agonists (**Fig. 1A and B**), published by Carson and colleagues,⁴ and have proven to be more potent than currently known TLR7 agonists in stimulating mammalian immune cells. Thus, they serve as promising candidates for boosting long lasting memory responses in mice.⁴

Liposomes are versatile drug carriers for a broad spectrum of hydrophobic, amphipathic, and hydrophilic drugs, including small drugs, peptides, proteins, and nucleic acids.⁵⁻⁷ Liposomes are known to be cleared by the mononuclear phagocyte system,⁸ but how liposomes interact with leucocytes is in need of further clarification.⁹⁻¹¹ Thus, we wanted to investigate the interactions of

liposomes with different populations of leukocytes in fresh human blood as a function of the physicochemical properties of the liposomes. Moreover, we investigated the use of liposomes for targeting TLR7 agonists specifically to monocytes with the aim of achieving a potent and specific immunological response. TMXs were chosen as the TLR7 agonists for the study due to their lipid based structure making them interesting for use in liposome formulations (**Fig. 1A** and **B**).

Materials and Methods

Materials

2-(4- {[6-Amino-2-(2-methoxyethoxy)-8-oxo-7H-purin-9(8H)-yl]methyl}benzamido)ethyl 2,3-Bis(oleoyloxy)propyl phosphate and 2-(4- {[6-Amino-2-(2-methoxyethoxy)-8-oxo-7H-purin-9(8H)-yl]methyl}benzamido)ethyl 2,3- Bis(dodecanoyloxy)propyl phosphate are abbreviated in this article as TMX-201 and TMX-202 (**Fig. 1A** and **B**), respectively. TMXs refer to TMX-201 and TMX-202. TMXs' and hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HPBCD) were supplied by Telormedix (Bioggio, CH). The lipids 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (POPC), cholesterol (Chol), 1,2-dioleoyl-3-trimethylammonium-propane (DOTAP), Dimethyldioctadecylammonium (DDA) bromide and 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine-N-rhodamine (DOPE-Rhod) were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, AL).

Methanol, ethanol (EtOH), chloroform, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), tetrahydrofuran (THF), trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), sucrose, glucose, HEPES, citric acid, calcium gluconate, PBS buffer, fetal bovine serum (FBS), and 1,6-diphenyl-1,3,5-hexatriene (DPH) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). PD-10 columns, Sephadex-G25 and Sepharose DEAE CL-6B were purchased from GE Healthcare Life Science (Piscataway, NJ).

Characterization of TMX-201 and TMX-202

Calculator Plugins, Marvin 5.9.1, 2012 ChemAxon (Budapest, HU) was used in order to calculate the pK_a , $\log D$ and charge of the molecules; ChemBioOffice 2010 (CambridgeSoft Corporation,

Cambridge, MA) was used for calculation of the three dimensional conformations in water as previously described.¹²

The solubility of TMX-201 and TMX-202 in different solvents was qualitatively evaluated by visual inspection. The TMXs were dissolved in the appropriate solvent and mixed by vortexing at room temperature. If aggregates were observed, then bath sonication was applied. The solubility was classified into three categories: soluble ≥ 40 mg/ml, slightly soluble 1 mg/ml, and insoluble <0.1 mg/ml.

Liposome preparation

Liposomes composed of POPC, DOTAP or DDA, Chol, and TMX-201 or TMX-202 were prepared by ethanol injection (EI) and lipid film hydration (LFH) methods. For some preparations, 0.25% DOPE-Rhod was added for labeling purposes. Low concentrations of liposomes (< 16 mM of lipid) were prepared by EI,¹³ while higher concentrations were prepared by LFH.¹⁴ The following aqueous buffers were used: Sucrose 290 mM, HEPES 10 mM, pH 7.4 (Sucrose buffer); Sucrose 290 mM, citrate 10 mM, EDTA and ascorbic acid 0.1 mM, pH 5.0 (SCEA buffer); and phosphate 10 mM, NaCl 138 mM, KCl 2.7 mM, pH 7.4 (PBS buffer).

For the EI method, a mixture of lipids was dissolved in ethanol:DMSO 4:1 at a concentration of 150-180 mM, and then injected into an aqueous buffer. For the LFH method, a mixture of lipids was dissolved in chloroform:methanol (9:1, w/w), mixed, and dried under a gentle stream of nitrogen at 35°C. The lipid film was thoroughly dried to remove residual organic solvent by a vacuum oil-pump overnight. Finally, the dry film was hydrated in an aqueous buffer for 1 h at 45 °C, and then 3 freeze-thaw cycles were applied.

The size of the liposomes was controlled by medium-pressure stepwise extrusion through polycarbonate membranes (400, 200, and 100 nm pore size) using an Avanti[®] mini-extruder in a heating block (Avanti Polar Lipids, Alabaster, Alabama) at 45 °C.

Ion exchange chromatography (IEC) through PD-10 columns with Sepharose CL-6B was used in order to purify the cationic liposomes from free TMXs and ethanol (**Supplementary Fig. S1**). Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) through PD-10 columns with Sephadex G-25 was used for the purification of neutral or anionic liposomes

Measurement of size, polydispersity index and zeta potential

The hydrodynamic diameter and polydispersity (PDI) were measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) using the ZetaPALS of Brookhaven Instruments Corporation (Holtsville, New York). The liposomes were diluted in a sterile and filtrated PBS buffer to a final concentration of 60-110 μM lipid, which gave count rates of 250-500 kcps. The Zeta-potential was measured by laser-Doppler electrophoresis using ZetaPALS. The liposomes were diluted in a sterile and filtrated glucose buffer (Glucose 300 mM, HEPES 10 mM pH 7.4, Calcium Gluconate 1 mM). The samples were degassed and left for equilibration at room temperature (RT) in the buffers for at least 10 min before the measurement.

Determination of lipid concentration

The lipid concentration was estimated by measurement of the fluorescence intensity of DOPE-rhod at excitation/emission wavelengths of 570/610 nm using Victor 3 plate reader of Perkin Elmer (Waltham, MA). The liposomes were dissolved in isopropanol with 75 mM of HCl (IPA) to a final concentration of 7-50 μM of lipid (final volume per well was 300 μl). Each sample was measured in triplicates, and a blank measurement of pure IPA was subtracted from each sample. The lipid concentration of an unknown sample was calculated according to a calibration curve.

Phospholipid concentrations were measured by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) for liposomes that did not contain Rhod-DOPE. Liposomes were diluted to a final phosphate concentration of 25-95 PPB in a solution of HCl 2% and Gallium 10 PPB, and the phosphate concentration was measured by ICP-MS (iCap Q, Thermo Scientific).

Quantification of TMXs by high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC)

The following HPLC system was used: Pump 321, Auto injector 234, and UV detector 155 (Gilson, WI). An Xbridge TM C18, 5 μm , 4.6 x 150 mm column was used. The column temperature was set to 30 °C. All samples were dissolved in water:tetrahydrofuran (THF) 1:1. The injection volume was 20 μl . A gradient program was used: 0.5 \rightarrow 20 min: increase from 20% to 68% of THF (in water), 20-21 min: hold 68% of THF, 21.1 min: back to 20% of THF, 25 min: end run. Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) was added to all the solvents of the mobile phase at a final concentration of 0.1% (pH control). The flow rate was 1 ml/min, and the UV detector was set to 293 nm (**Supplementary Fig. S2**). The elution times of TMX-201 and TMX-202 under these conditions were 20.7 min and 17.0 min, respectively. Calibration curves of TMXs at concentration of 0-100 mg/l were prepared. The liposomes with TMXs were diluted by 20-120 folds before the injection.

The encapsulation efficiency of TMXs was calculated using formula 1:

$$(1) \text{ Encapsulation\%} = 100 \times \frac{([\text{TMX}]/[\text{lipid}]_{\text{after IEC}})}{([\text{TMX}]/[\text{lipid}]_{\text{hydration}})}$$

Microviscosities of lipid membranes

The degree of liposome membrane microviscosity was measured by fluorescence polarization (P) of the fluorophore 1,6-diphenyl-1,3,5-hexatriene (DPH).^{15,16} The DPH was added to the liposomes formulation (final mole ratio of total lipid to probe was 500:1), followed by 1 h incubation in the dark at 37 °C to achieve complete insertion of the DPH into the hydrophobic region of the liposome bilayer. The degree of DPH polarization in the labeled liposomes in PBS was measured using OLIS[®] refurbished SLM fluorimeter (Bogart, CA) at excitation/emission wavelengths of 365/430 nm was measured at 37 °C. The microviscosity ($\bar{\eta}$) was calculated according to formula 2:¹⁷

$$(2) \bar{\eta} = \frac{2P}{0.46 - P}$$

Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight (MALDI-TOF)

Lipid stocks of 1 mg/ml in chloroform were prepared. The lipids of the liposomes were extracted by Bligh and Dryer method¹⁸ as described in the supplementary Data. The following matrix was used: 2,5-dihydroxy-benzoic acid 60 g/l in methanol spiked with potassium TFA. 30 µl of the lipid solution were mixed with 30 µl of the matrix. Half µl of this mixture was uploaded onto the MALDI plate. Bruker Reflex IV MALDI-TOF Spectrometer was used. Two hundred shots per run and 15% of laser power were used.

Evaluation of TMX release from liposomes

Liposomes composed of POPC:DOTAP:TMX 81:14:5 were stored for 2 months at 4° C. In addition, liposomes were diluted in FBS to a final FBS concentration of 55%, and they were mixed thoroughly. Fresh and old liposomes were purified by IEC as described in the liposomes preparation section. The lipids of the liposomes that were incubated with FBS were extracted by Bligh and Dyer method. The TMX to lipid ratio was compared before and after the IEC, and TMX release from the liposomes was calculated according to formula 3:

$$(3) \text{ TMX release \%} = 100 \times \left(1 - \frac{[\text{TMX}]/[\text{lipid}]^{\text{after IEC}}}{[\text{TMX}]/[\text{lipid}]^{\text{before IEC}}} \right)$$

Uptake of liposomes by immune cells in human blood

Peripheral blood was obtained from healthy volunteers in BD Vacutainer containing EDTA.

Liposomal preparations (2 - 20 µL) were added to 200 µL fresh blood in 2 mL Eppendorf tubes.

Samples incubated 1, 2 or 4 hours at 37 °C with rotation. Red blood cells (RBC) were lysed in 4 mL BD Pharm lysis buffer in the dark at room temperature (RT) for 15 min in 15 ml tubes, centrifuged at 300 g for 5 min. Supernatants were aspirated and samples resuspended in 4 mL PBS supplemented with 1 % heat inactivated FBS. Samples were centrifuged at 300 g for 5 min and

resuspended in 50 μ L FACS buffer. Unspecific binding were blocked by human IgG for 10 min on ice before the cells were incubated in 100 μ L FACS buffer with primary pre-conjugated antibody or isotype control for 20 min on ice, and centrifuged at 300 g for 5 min at 4 °C. Cells were washed twice in 200 μ L FACS buffer. Cells were resuspended in 500 μ L FACS buffer, before being subjected to flow cytometric analysis, which were carried out on a BD FACSAria bioanalyzer. The total amount of liposome associated with cells was determined based on the fluorescence of DOPE-rhod. Liposomal association with five different leukocytes' cell populations was analyzed based on the following markers: CD14 (monocyte marker), CD15 (neutrophil granulocyte marker), CD3 (T lymphocyte marker), CD19 (B-lymphocyte marker), and CD56 (natural killer cell marker). Data were analyzed by FlowJo 7.6.1.

Activation of monocytes by free and liposomal TMXs

Whole blood from healthy human donors were treated with different concentrations (0.1, 1, or 10 μ M) of free TMXs, liposomes with TMXs, or Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) and incubated at 37 °C. The samples were initially incubated for 1 hour with rotation, followed by 23 hours without rotation. Hereafter the plasma was harvested and additional media was added to the samples (100 μ l per well) and further incubated for another 24 hours. The plasma after 24 hours was analyzed for IL-6 and IL-12p40 by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Results

Physiochemical characterization of TMX-201 and TMX-202 liposomes

The TMX compounds have two identical ionizable groups (**Fig. 1A and B**): a phosphate (pK_a 1.9) and a purine (pK_a 11.8). The molecules are very hydrophobic but negatively charged at physiological pH (**Fig. 1C and D**). Their calculated three dimensional conformations in water (Inserts in **Fig. 1A and B**) indicate that the methoxyethoxy, purine and phosphate groups align to

one side, while the hydrocarbons and the benzene groups align to the opposite side. TMXs were found to be insoluble in water (self-associates), PBS buffer, and methanol (**Table 1**), but soluble in DMSO, tetrahydrofuran (THF), and HPBCD 20% in water. The average diameters of the self-associated TMX-201 and TMX-202 particles in water were 200-300 nm and 700-750 nm, respectively, with relatively high polydispersity, while the zeta potentials of both particles were highly negative, (-63) – (-85) mV (**Supplementary Table S1**).

Preparation and characterization of various liposomal formulations of TMXs

The zeta potential of a number of different liposomal formulations of POPC, Chol, DOTAP, TMX-201, and TMX-202 was measured (**Fig. 2**). As expected, increasing the DOTAP concentration led to an increase in zeta potential (**Fig. 2a**). Adding Chol to the membrane did not affect the zeta potential, while incorporation of TMX-201 (**Fig. 2b**) or TMX-202 (**Fig. 2c**) into the membrane reduced the zeta potential of the cationic liposomes. In all cases, liposomes with TMX-202 were more positively charged than liposomes with TMX-201 (same percentage of TMXs). The charge difference between liposomes with TMX-201 and TMX-202 is small at low concentrations of TMXs (2-5%) but it is large at high concentration of TMXs (10-20%).

The microviscosities of the lipid membranes of liposomal formulations of POPC, Chol, DOTAP, DDA, TMX-201, and TMX-202 were measured (**Fig. 3**). Increase in DOTAP or TMX-201 mole ratios (substituting POPC) reduced the viscosity. However, increase in DDA or TMX-202 mole ratios (substituting POPC) increased the viscosity. Furthermore, addition of cholesterol instead of POPC increased the viscosity dramatically as expected.

The diameter and the polydispersity (PDI) of liposomal formulations of POPC, DOTAP, TMX-201, and TMX-202 were measured (**Fig. 4**). The size and the PDI of the liposomes showed dependence on the difference between DOTAP and TMX concentrations. For liposomal formulations of TMX,

where $\text{DOTAP}\% - \text{TMX}\% \geq 7\%$, the size and the PDI did not increase in comparison with empty liposomes (liposomes without TMX). However, in liposomal formulations of TMX, in which $\text{DOTAP}\% - \text{TMX}\% \leq 6\%$, the size and the polydispersity increased. This increase was more dramatic for liposomal formulations of TMX-202 than liposomal formulations of TMX-201. The encapsulation efficiency of TMX-201 and TMX-202 into cationic liposomes was measured by purifying the liposomes by IEC, and was found to be 90-100%.

Storage stability

Liposomal formulations of TMX, where $\text{DOTAP}\% - \text{TMX}\% \leq 6\%$, precipitated when stored in PBS (**Supplementary Fig. S3**). This precipitation was not observed when the liposomes were stored in sucrose buffer. Liposomal formulations of TMX, where $\text{DOTAP}\% - \text{TMX}\% > 6\%$, did not precipitate when stored in PBS. The diameters (**Supplementary Fig. S4**) and the zeta potentials (**Supplementary Fig. S5**) of the liposomal TMX-201 and liposomal TMX-202 have not changed during 80 days of storage at 4 °C.

TLC analysis for detection of lipid degradation to lysolipids showed no signs of degradation during 4 months of storage at 4 °C (**Supplementary Fig. S6**). We experimentally estimated that the TLC assay was only sensitive for more than 10% degradation. Therefore, we also did MALDI-TOF analysis, which was confirmed to be especially sensitive to lysolipids.¹⁹ An initial MALDI-TOF analysis confirmed that the different liposome components have different peaks (**Supplementary Fig. S7**). Next, we confirmed that we can detect the lysolipids in a mixture of lipids that were extracted from the liposomes by Bligh and Dyer extraction (**Supplementary Fig. S8**). Finally, lipids from liposomes were extracted from liposomes after different periods of storage. The MALDI-TOF analysis of these lipids indicated that the degradation of the lipids to lysolipids did not seem to increase over time (**Fig. 5**).

We also confirmed that TMXs were not released from the liposomes during two months storage at 4° C. Moreover, incubation of the liposomes with serum did not lead to TMX release from the liposomes.

Relation between physicochemical properties of liposomes and targeting to immune cells

Liposomes association with monocytes in whole human blood

We wanted to elucidate how variations in liposomal surface charge affected the association of liposomes with monocytes. Therefore, liposomes with increasing DOTAP concentrations and zeta potentials were incubated with freshly drawn human blood for 1 h at 37 °C. Liposomes with a zeta potential of 0-24 mv did not associate with leukocytes (**Fig. 6**, left y-axis). Liposomes with a zeta potential of 30-41 mV showed a strong preferential association with CD14⁺ monocytes, compared to other leukocytes (T and B lymphocytes, natural killer, and neutrophils), which is demonstrated by liposome uptake by monocytes to other leukocytes ratio of 10-31 (**Fig. 6**, right y-axis).

Increasing the zeta potential of the liposomes to 47 mV resulted in enhanced monocyte-association with approximately 90 % of the cells associated with liposomes, however, the proportion of liposome associated with other leukocytes increased and approximately 18 % were liposome positive, therefore the monocyte to other leukocyte targeting ratio decreased to 5. Further increasing the zeta potential of the liposomes to 57 mV showed 95 % association with monocytes and approximate 41 % association with other leukocytes, thereby abrogating the preferential association of the liposomes to monocytes. At zeta potential of 74 mV, the liposomes associated strongly with all leukocytes. Thus, liposomes containing 10 % DOTAP, with a zeta-potential between 30 - 41 mV, showed the strongest monocyte specific association.

Effect of microviscosity on immune cell targeting

Liposomes with microviscosities of 0.8 – 3 poise were incubated with fresh human blood. Two anionic and 11 cationic formulations were compared. Mainly monocytes were targeted by the cationic formulations after 1 h incubation in fresh human whole blood (**Fig. 7**). The targeting specificity of the cationic liposomes towards monocytes in whole blood samples was not dependent on the microviscosity of the membranes. Moreover, the addition of cholesterol did not significantly alter the performance of liposomes with respect to monocyte specificity, although the microviscosity was significantly increased. Lymphocytes and granulocytes were targeted from 10-30 % of the population with the different positively charged formulations (based on side-scattered and forward scattered light gating).

Effect of liposomes size on immune cell targeting

Liposomes with diameters of ~100, 200, and 400 nm but similar zeta potentials (~38 mV) were incubated with fresh human blood. The liposomes of 100 and 200 nm in size targeted monocytes significantly more efficient than the liposomes of 400 nm (**Supplementary Fig. 9**). The 100 nm liposomes seemed to target the monocytes slightly better than the 200 nm liposomes but the difference was not statistically significant. In addition, the percentage of CD14⁺ monocytes that associated with the liposomes decreased over time for all liposomes sizes, and the maximal association was achieved after 1 h incubation.

In vitro studies of cytokine induction

Secretion of the cytokines IL-12p40 and IL-6 were analyzed in the blood after incubation in fresh human blood with free TMXs, compared to different formulations of the TLR agonists. IL-12p40 is a typical T-helper cell type 1 activating cytokine, which is produced by monocytes or monocytes differentiated to myeloid dendritic cells, while IL-6 is produced by many different cell types including monocytes, macrophages, and B-cells.

Various TMX-201 liposomes with the optimal cationic surface charge range in **Fig. 6**, induced IL-12p40 slightly more efficient than free TMX-201, while TMX-202 liposomes induced IL-12p40 significantly more efficient than free TMX-202 (**Fig. 8A**). In particular, liposomes composed of POPC:Chol:DDA:TMX-202 induced the highest levels of both IL-6 and IL-12p40 to levels 20-30 folds above what was seen for the free TMX-202 (**Fig. 8A and B**). In contrast, neither negatively charged liposomal TMX (POPC:TMX liposomes) nor empty liposomes could induce significant secretions of IL-6 and IL-12p40. The cytokine secretion by the monocytes was positively correlated with the concentration of the adjuvant.

The secretion of IL-12p40 cytokine was measured after addition of liposomes with different sizes to fresh human whole blood (**Supplementary Fig. 10**). Neither free TMX-202 nor empty liposomes induced IL-12p40 secretion. Only liposomes with TMX-202 induced secretion of IL-12p40. Albeit, a negative linear correlation was observed between the stimulation of the cytokine secretion and the liposome diameter, i.e. the smaller liposomes induced more IL-12p40 secretion than larger liposomes.

Discussion

The highly negative zeta potentials of the TMX liposomes in water (**Supplementary Table S1**) can be explained by their negative charge at physiological pH (**Fig. 1A and B**), and fit with the charge predictions (**Fig. 1C**). The three dimensional conformations of TMXs in water (Inserts in **Fig. 1A and B**) together with the high $\log D$ s (**Fig. 1D**) and solubility profiles (**Table 1**) suggest that TMXs are good candidates for incorporation in the membrane of cationic liposomes. The association of TMXs with the cationic liposomes is likely based on hydrophobic interactions between the hydrocarbon chain, with a potential hydrophobic contribution from the phenyl ring on the TMXs, and an electrostatic interaction between the negatively charged phosphate and the cationic lipids.

The zeta potential of liposomes is controlled by the balance between the cationic and anionic lipids (**Fig. 2**). The negatively and the positively charged lipids neutralize each other approximately linearly (for instance, liposomes with DOTAP 10% have the same zeta potential as liposomes with DOTAP 14% and TMX-202 5%). However, the zeta potential cannot be accurately predicted just by the charge of polar head groups, since various other factors influence the zeta potential. This is exemplified by the slightly negative zeta potential of the liposomes POPC:DOTAP:TMX-201 81:9:10 (**Fig. 2**) but slightly positive zeta potential of POPC:DOTAP:TMX-202 81:9:10. In addition, we observed that the zeta potential of POPC:DDA 9:1 is higher than POPC:DOTAP 9:1. Liposomal membranes can acquire different phases as a function of temperature, e.g. the liquid-disordered (LD) phase has the highest fluidity and highest free volume. The solid ordered (SO) phase is more ordered, more viscous, and has the lowest free volume. The main phase transition temperature (T_m) between these phases is higher for saturated lipids than for unsaturated lipids. Mixtures of a liposome-forming lipid and cholesterol at a mole % of >30 result in a different phase, referred to as liquid-ordered (LO) phase, which is a highly viscous fluid phase. There is a difference in the LO phase based on a high T_m or a low T_m lipids where the high T_m LO phase is significantly less permeable than low T_m LO phase.²⁰ Therefore, addition of TMX-202, DDA, and cholesterol to the liposomes increased the microviscosity (**Fig. 3**).

Chemical hydrolysis has previously been reported for cationic liposomes upon storage in aqueous dispersion.²¹ Good storage stability of the liposomes was achieved in this study (see Fig 5. and supplementary **Fig. 4-6**) by the use of high quality lipids (purified from hydroperoxides and transition metals), the use of freshly degassed solvents, avoidance of procedures that involve high temperatures or sonication, addition of antioxidant (ascorbic acid) and a transition metal ion chelator (EDTA), and storage of liposomes at low temperatures and protected from light.²²

The Stern potential of colloids, ϕ_δ , can be controlled by varying the surface potential, ϕ_0 , which in turn is determined by the relative concentration of ions. While ϕ_0 -values of cationic liposomes may exceed 200 mV, such high values strongly attract counterion binding in the Stern layer, and one

seldom encounters Zeta potentials (experimental estimation of φ_{δ}) in excess of 80 mV.²³ Hence, the potential barrier for colloids aggregation decreases sharply with increase in electrolyte concentration.²⁴ Therefore, in some cases storage of cationic liposomes in sucrose buffer can prevent liposomes from precipitation (**Supplementary Fig. S3**).

We have found that the selective targeting to monocyte of the optimized cationic liposomes decreases as a function of the time after blood drawing. Therefore, we hypothesize that the targeting mechanism may involve the complement system, which contains factors with relatively short half-life in blood. Characterization of the blood proteins associated with liposomes recovered from the blood of liposome-treated mice indicate that cationic liposomes are capable of activating the alternative complement pathway in human blood,²⁵ resulting in the association of opsonic C3 fragments with the liposome membrane. Moreover, the amount of C3 associated per liposome relates to their observed circulation clearance properties *in vivo*; liposomes bearing elevated C3 levels per liposome are cleared more rapidly.²⁶ The degradation products C3b and C3bi play an important role in the initial rapid phase of *in vivo* clearance of certain liposomes and the rate of clearance of liposomes may depend on their ability to activate the complement system.²⁷ Monocytes have CR3 and CR4 receptors which are specific for iC3b and stimulate phagocytosis.²⁸

It was previously reported that increase in the membrane rigidity of liposomes decreases the uptake of liposomes by macrophages in tissue culture.²⁹ However, the targeting of our charge optimized cationic liposomes to monocytes was independent of membrane viscosity (**Fig. 3 and 7**). Unlike negatively charged liposomes, which are more efficiently taken up by monocytes, when they are large,³⁰ our cationic liposomes target monocytes better when they are small (**Supplementary Fig. S9 and S10**). Although negatively charged liposomes have been shown to associate with monocytes, they did not activate the complement system.³⁰ Therefore, our viscosity and size results indicate that the monocyte targeting mechanism of our charge optimized cationic liposomes is different from previously reported negatively charged liposomes, and could potentially involve complement activation.

The superiority of the liposomal TMXs over the free TMXs in activation of monocytes (**Fig. 8**) suggests that these new liposomes could be used for treatment of diseases that depend on monocyte activation or the differentiation of monocytes into dendritic cells or macrophages, such as cancer immunotherapy⁴ and vaccination against bacterial or viral infections.³¹ As compared to other adjuvants, DDA alone is a moderate or strong adjuvant for humoral responses. DDA (and several other cationic lipids) can enhance the effect of other immune stimulating compounds or adjuvants.³² Thus, the liposomal TMX-202 formulation was especially potent in activating monocytes to produce the Th1-inducing cytokine IL-12p40, which is important for a strong T-cell response (**Fig. 8**). In addition, the present targeting technology is significantly cheaper and easier in scale-up, than other targeting technologies using liposomes or nanoparticles with ligand or antibody directed targeting, which binds specifically to a receptor on the target cells.³³

Conclusions

TLR7 agonists can be incorporated into the liposomal membrane by hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions with high encapsulation efficiency. By rational adjustment of the liposome zeta potential to 30-41 mV and the diameter to 100-200 nm, the liposomes enable specific targeting to monocytes in fresh human blood. A broad range of membrane microviscosity (0.9 – 3 poise) is suitable for the monocyte targeting. Moreover, liposomes with a zeta potential in the 30-41 mV range formulated with TLR7 agonists enhance the monocyte activation 3-4 fold for TMX-201, and more than 30 fold for TMX-202 in fresh whole human blood, in comparison to the activation level of free TMX-201 and TMX-202. Therefore, these novel immune stimulating liposomes are promising candidates for immunotherapy of cancer and vaccination against infectious disease.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the European Eurostars Programme (Project acronym: LIPODEL). In addition, we would like to thank the Danish–Israeli Study Foundation in Memory of Josef and Regine Nachemsohn for additional funding.

Supplementary material is available

References

1. Smith, DM, Simon, JK and Baker Jr JR (2013). Applications of nanotechnology for immunology. *Nat Rev Immunol* **13**: 592-605.
2. Kanzler, H, Barrat, FJ, Hessel, EM and Coffman, RL (2007). Therapeutic targeting of innate immunity with Toll-like receptor agonists and antagonists. *Nat Med* **13**: 552-559.
3. Hirsch, I, Caux, C, Hasan, U, Bendriss-Vermare, N and Olive, D (2010). Impaired Toll-like receptor 7 and 9 signaling: from chronic viral infections to cancer. *Trends Immunol* **31**: 391-397.
4. Chan, M, Hayashi, T, Kuy, CS, Gray, CS, Wu, CC, Corr, M et al. (2009). Synthesis and immunological characterization of toll-like receptor 7 agonistic conjugates. *Bioconjugate Chem* **20**: 1194-1200.
5. Barenholz, Y and Crommelin, D (1994). Liposomes as pharmaceutical dosage forms. In: Swarbrick J, Boylan J, editors. *Encyclopedia of Pharmaceutical Technology*. New York: Marcel Dekker Inc, p. 1-39.
6. Gjetting, T, Andresen, TL, Christensen, CL, Cramer, F, Poulsen, TT and Poulsen, HS (2011). A simple protocol for preparation of a liposomal vesicle with encapsulated plasmid DNA that mediate high accumulation and reporter gene activity in tumor tissue. *Results Pharma Sci* **1**: 49-56.
7. Zucker, D, Marcus, D, Barenholz, Y and Goldblum, A (2009). Liposome drugs' loading efficiency: a working model based on loading conditions and drug's physicochemical properties. *J Control Release* **139**: 73-80.
8. Gabizon, A, Chisin, R, Amselem, S, Druckmann, S, Cohen, R, Goren, D, et al. (1991). Pharmacokinetic and imaging studies in patients receiving a formulation of liposome-associated adriamycin. *Brit J Cancer* **64**: 1125.
9. Constantinescu, I, Levin, E and Gyongyossy-Issa, M (2003). Liposomes and blood cells: a flow cytometric study. *Artif Cell Blood Sub* **31**: 395-424.
10. Karathanasis, E, Geigerman, CM, Parkos, CA, Chan, L, Bellamkonda, RV and Jaye DL (2009). Selective targeting of nanocarriers to neutrophils and monocytes. *Ann Biomed Eng* **37**: 1984-1992.

11. Kuhn, SH, Gemperli, B, Shephard, EG, Joubert, JR, Weidemann, PA, Weissmann, G, et al. (1983). Interaction of liposomes with human leukocytes in whole blood. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **762**: 119-127.
12. Blume, G and Cevc, G (1990). Liposomes for the sustained drug release in vivo. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **1029**: 91-97.
13. Batzri, S and Korn, ED (1973). Single bilayer liposomes prepared without sonication. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **298**: 1015-1019.
14. Bangham, AD, Standish, MM and Watkins, JC (1965). Diffusion of univalent ions across the lamellae of swollen phospholipids. *J Mol Biol*, **13**: 238-272.
15. Shinitzky, M and Barenholz, Y (1974). Dynamics of the Hydrocarbon Layer in Liposomes of Lecithin and Sphingomyelin Containing Dicaprylylphosphate. *J Biol Chem* **249**: 2652-2657.
16. Zucker, D, Andriyanov, AV, Steiner, A, Raviv, U and Barenholz, Y (2012). Characterization of PEGylated nanoliposomes co-remotely loaded with topotecan and vincristine: relating structure and pharmacokinetics to therapeutic efficacy. *J Control Release* **160**: 281-289.
17. Shinitzky, M and Barenholz, Y (1978). Fluidity parameters of lipid regions determined by fluorescence polarization. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **515**: 367-394.
18. Bligh, E and Dyer, WJ (1959). A rapid method of total lipid extraction and purification. *Can J Biochem Physiol* **37**: 911-917.
19. Schiller, J, Süß, R, Arnhold, J, Fuchs, B, Leßig, J, Müller, M et al. (2004) Matrix-assisted laser desorption and ionization time-of-flight (MALDI-TOF) mass spectrometry in lipid and phospholipid research. *Prog Lipid Res* **43**: 449-488.
20. Zucker, D (2010). Relevant lipids' biophysics and selection of suitable lipids. In: Barenholz, Y, editor. *Liposomes Loaded with Topotecan and Vincristine for Cancer Treatment*. Saarbrücken: VDM Verlag Dr. Müller, p. 19-25.

21. Zuidam, NJ and Barenholz, Y (1997). Electrostatic parameters of cationic liposomes commonly used for gene delivery as determined by 4-heptadecyl-7-hydroxycoumarin. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **1329**: 211-222.
22. Zuidam, NJ, Winden, EV, Vrueth, RD and Crommelin, DJ (2003). Stability, storage, and sterilization of liposomes. In: Torchilin VP, editor. *Liposomes - practical approach*. 2nd ed. New York: Oxford University Press, p. 149-154.
23. Hirsch-Lerner, D, Zhang, M, Eliyahu, H, Ferrari, ME, Wheeler, CJ and Barenholz, Y (2005). Effect of “helper lipid” on lipoplex electrostatics. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **1714**: 71-84.
24. Berg, JC (2009). Interaction between colloid particles. An introduction to interfaces and colloids Singapore: World Scientific Publishing, p. 540-559.
25. Devine, DV and Bradley, AJ (1998). The complement system in liposome clearance: Can complement deposition be inhibited? *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* **32**: 19-29.
26. Semple, SC, Chonn, A and Cullis, PR (1998). Interactions of liposomes and lipid-based carrier systems with blood proteins: Relation to clearance behaviour in vivo. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* **32**: 3-17.
27. Moghimi, SM and Patel, HM (1998). Serum-mediated recognition of liposomes by phagocytic cells of the reticuloendothelial system – The concept of tissue specificity. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* **32**: 45-60.
28. Murphy, K (2007). The complement system and innate immunity. *Janeway's Immunobiology* New York: Garland Science, p. 74.
29. Allen, TM, Austin, GA, Chonn, A, Lin, L, Lee, KC (1991). Uptake of liposomes by cultured mouse bone marrow macrophages: influence of liposome composition and size. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, **1061**: 56-64.
30. Epstein-Barash, H, Gutman, D, Markovsky, E, Mishan-Eisenberg, G, Koroukhov, N, Szebeni, J et al. (2010). Physicochemical parameters affecting liposomal bisphosphonates bioactivity for

restenosis therapy: Internalization, cell inhibition, activation of cytokines and complement, and mechanism of cell death. *J Control Release* **146**: 182-195.

31. Krutzik, SR, Tan, B, Li, H, Ochoa, MT, Liu, PT, Sharfstein, SE, et al. (2005). TLR activation triggers the rapid differentiation of monocytes into macrophages and dendritic cells. *Nat Med* **11**: 653-660.

32. Hilgers, LA and Snippe, H (1992). DDA as an immunological adjuvant. *Research in immunology* **143**: 494-503.

33. Emanuel, N, Kedar, E, Bolotin, EM, Smorodinsky, NI and Barenholz, Y (1996). Targeted delivery of doxorubicin via sterically stabilized immunoliposomes: pharmacokinetics and biodistribution in tumor-bearing mice. *Pharm Res* **13**: 861-868.

Table 1. Solubility of TMX-201 and TMX-202 in different solvents

Solvent	TMX-201	TMX-202
Water	insoluble	insoluble
HPBCD 20% in water	soluble	soluble
PBS pH 7.4	insoluble	insoluble
Methanol	insoluble	insoluble
Ethanol	insoluble	slightly soluble
DMSO	soluble	soluble
Tetrahydrofuran	soluble	soluble

Figure Captions

Figure 1. Chemical characterization of TMXs. A and B) Chemical structures of TMX-201 and TMX-202, respectively. Their molecular weights (M_w), and pK_a s (phosphate and purine groups) are indicated. Inserts in A and B) Three dimensional conformations of TMX-201 and TMX-202, respectively, in water in a space filling display. To obtain the structural form in space a molecular optimization procedure using MM2 force field has been performed for TMX-201 and TMX-202 with 20 adjacent water molecules; the latter were omitted in this representation for the sake of clarity. C and D) Charge and $\log D$, respectively, of TMXs as a function of pH.

Figure 2. Zeta potentials of liposomes (diameter of 200 nm) composed of POPC, DOTAP, Chol, TMX-201, and TMX-202 at various mole ratios. A) Effect of DOTAP concentration on the zeta potential. B and C) Effect of TMX-201 and TMX-202, respectively, concentrations on the zeta potential. The mole % of different lipid components of the various liposomal formulations is shown next to the lipid abbreviation. TMX-201 and TMX-202 are abbreviated as T1 and T2, respectively, in the labels on the y-axis.

Figure 3. Microviscosities of the lipid membranes of liposomes composed of POPC, Chol, DOTAP, DDA, TMX-201, and TMX-202 at various mole ratios. The mole % of different lipid components of the various liposomal formulations is shown next to the lipid abbreviation. TMX-201 and TMX-202 are abbreviated as T1 and T2, respectively, in the labels on the y-axis.

Figure 4. Mean diameter and polydispersity of empty liposomes (POPC:DOTAP) and liposomal TMXs 2-20%. The Left y-axis and the column represent the diameter (gray columns), whereas the right y-axis represent the PDI (dark circles). TMX-201 and TMX-202 are abbreviated as T1 and T2, respectively, in the labels on the x-axis.

Figure 5. Positive ion MALDI-TOF mass spectrums of lipid mixtures, extracted from liposomes by Bligh and Dyer extraction, after different storage periods. Adducts' names and their exact molecular weights are mentioned above the relevant peaks. Significant formation of lysolipids was not

detected. The position of the main peak of lyso-C18 PC is marked with a blue arrow. A-C) Liposomes composed of POPC:DOTAP:TMX-201 at mole ratios of 81:14:5 after 0, 2 and 4 months of storage are shown on panels A, B, and C, respectively. D-F) Liposomes composed of POPC:DOTAP:TMX-202 at mole ratios of 81:14:5 after 0, 2 and 4 months of storage are shown on panels D, E, and F, respectively.

Figure 6. Effect of the zeta potential of liposomes on their association with leukocytes in fresh whole human blood. Data are expressed as percentages of cells positive for rhodamine B shown as mean \pm SD. The left y-axis represents the uptake of liposomes by monocytes and other leukocytes (T and B lymphocytes, natural killer, and neutrophils). The right y-axis represents the ratio between the uptakes of liposomes by monocytes and other leukocytes (targeting specificity).

Figure 7. Uptake of liposomes with different membrane microviscosity (X) by monocytes (black bars), lymphocytes (gray bars), and granulocytes (whit bars) after incubation of the liposomes with fresh human blood. The composition of the different liposomal formulations is described at the legends of the x-axis. The uptake of the liposomes is shown on the left y-axis, and the microviscosities of the liposomal formulations on the right y-axis.

Figure 8. Monocytes activation by free TMXs and liposomal TMXs. IL-12p40 (A) and IL-6 (B) cytokine secretion titers are shown as mean \pm SD of double measurements from three separate donors. The triangles at the X-axis designate increasing concentrations of TMXs 0.1, 1, and 10 μ M. The diameters of all liposomes were \sim 200 nm. TMX-201 and TMX-202 are abbreviated as T1 and T2, respectively, in the labels on the x-axis.

Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8